

COMPOSITES OF POLYPROPYLENE AND HYDROXYAPATITE: EFFECTS OF COPOLYMERS OF PROPYLENE AND ACRYLIC ACID ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY

The increased need for new materials resembling human bones has led the search for new composites of polymers and bioactive fillers. In this investigation, composites of polypropylene and hydroxyapatite were prepared. The influence of adding copolymers of propylene and acrylic acid on the mechanical properties of the composites is presented.

Keywords: PP composites, hydroxyapatite, PP/AA copolymers, bone substitution, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

From quite some time, researchers have been looking for materials that can act as bone substitutes. Such materials must not produce inflammatory reactions or carcinogenic effects and must resist sterilization conditions. Among them, composites of polyolefins with hydroxyapatite, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, have emerged as promising alternatives. Polyolefins cannot interact by themselves effectively with living tissues. Hence, hydroxyapatite (HA), a material highly compatible with those of bones and bioactive, has been incorporated into polyethylene and polypropylene to obtain bone implants or substitutes [1-3]. In fact, hydroxyapatite is one of the major components of human bones.

These composites comprise a polymeric ductile matrix and a stiffer ceramic dispersed phase. However, some incompatibility problems arise when hydroxyapatite is mixed with non-polar polymers. Thus, to obtain an effective compatibility between the hydroxyapatite and the polyolefin, a third component has to be incorporated into the composite. This compatibilizer must contribute to promote the interaction among the phases. Albano et al. have incorporated coupling agents [4,5], functionalized polyolefins [6] and copolymers of ethylene-acrylic acid [7] into composites of high-density polyethylene and HA. In the last two groups of materials, the methyl groups are intended to interact with the polymeric matrix and the carboxylic groups with the filler.

In this investigation, composites of polypropylene (PP) and hydroxyapatite were prepared. The influence of adding copolymers of propylene and acrylic acid on the mechanical and thermal properties of the composites is presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

Composites of polypropylene (PP) and hydroxyapatite (HA) were prepared, using two copolymers of propylene and acrylic acid, to promote their compatibility. A commercial grade polypropylene (MFR = 7.0 dg/min; $M_w = 248392$ g/mol) from Propilven, and two random block copolymers of propylene and acrylic acid (PP/AA copolymers, Polybond® 1001 and 1002), supplied by SpecialChem, were employed. Their characteristics are shown in Table 1. Nanometric HA was prepared through a precipitation reaction between calcium hydroxide, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, and ammonium phosphate, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ solutions, according to a method described in the literature [8]. Calcium hydroxide was purchased from Mallinckrodt and ammonium phosphate was supplied by Fischer Scientific. The resultant solution was centrifuged and washed with deionized water until neutral pH to finally being vacuum dried at 65 °C for 48 hours.

Composites of PP were prepared in a Haake Rheomix internal mixer at 190 °C. After the PP was melted at 50 rpm, the copolymers were added (10 phr of the polymer matrix). Following the complete melting of the polymeric phase, the HA (30 wt.% of PP matrix), previously dried, was incorporated. The rotors frequency was then increased up to 90 rpm for 8 more minutes, when the composite was discharged from the mixer.

Characterization

Morphological studies of the synthesized HA were carried out using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), Hitachi FE-5400. The surface of the HA was coated with gold by the ionic deposition method. Tensile tests were performed in an Instron 4204 universal testing machine at a cross speed of 1 mm/min, in specimens cut out from compression-molded sheets whose dimensions followed ASTM-638 standard procedure. Each tensile parameter reported represents an average of at least seven samples tested under identical conditions.

The thermal properties of the composites were determined through Differential Scanning Calorimetry under nitrogen gas. Analyses were carried out in a Mettler-Toledo DSC 822°. Samples (9-10 mg) were heated up to 200°C and kept at that temperature for about 3 min in order to erase the previous thermal history. This initial heating was performed at a rate of 20 °C/min. Afterwards, the samples were cooled down to room temperature and subsequently heated up to 200 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min. Parameters were determined from the first cooling and second heating cycles. The crystallinity degree was then calculated.

Thermal decomposition analyses were carried out to study the thermal stability of the composites. The E_2 -function method, proposed by Chen et al. [9], was employed to estimate the activation energy (E_a). Samples of 5-6 mg were heated in a Mettler-Toledo TGA/STDA 851° analyzer from room temperature up to 700 °C at 10 °C/min, under nitrogen gas.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows a micrograph of the synthesized HA. Its average particle size is mainly of nanometric scale, as it was corroborated by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), where the average measured particle size was 20 x 60 nm. Since HA particles tend to agglomerate, the resultant HA powder was then subjected to a particle size distribution analysis which evidenced an average agglomerate size of 6.9 μm .

Figure 1. SEM Micrographs of HA particles.

PP composites revealed an increase of the Young's modulus and a decrease in the elongation at break with the addition of the filler (Table 2). However, the addition of the copolymers did not affect the mechanical properties. Improved mechanical properties and filler dispersion in the matrix were expected with the addition of the copolymers, as well as an increased interaction between the matrix and the filler through the AA's polar groups. Nonetheless, these two effects do not seem to be taking place. A possible explanation resides in the difference between the molecular weights between the PP matrix and the copolymers.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of the composites.

% HA	Copolymer	Young's Modulus (MPa)	σ_r (MPa)	ϵ_r (%)
0	0	1337.5 \pm 19.21	25.17 \pm 1.63	12.76 \pm 3.77
30	0	2108.32 \pm 1.43	20.68 \pm 1.43	1.56 \pm 0.33
30	10 (Polybond® 1001)	2074.16 \pm 90.47	21.08 \pm 2.66	1.29 \pm 0.15
30	10 (Polybond® 1002)	2137.14 \pm 70.42	20.64 \pm 2.54	1.36 \pm 0.28

Table 3 displays the thermal properties of the composites. As it can be seen, the crystallinity degree of PP decreased when the HA was incorporated. Wang and Liu [10] attributed this fact to a hindered crystallization process in the presence of HA particles. The melting and crystallization temperatures remained unchanged in the presence of HA. When the compatibilizing agents were included, the crystallinity degree of the blend PP/compatibilizer without HA decreased, due to lower crystallinity degrees of the

copolymers. On the other hand, composites containing the compatibilizing agents displayed higher crystallization temperatures and crystallinity degrees than the composite without the copolymers. This fact can be attributed to a nucleating effect of the HA in presence of the compatibilizer, which in turn, could be a consequence of a slight increase in the degree of compatibility and/or dispersion of the filler. However, this increase did not modify the mechanical properties of the composites, and thus, a real interaction between the polymeric phase and the filler cannot be ascertained.

Table 3. Thermal properties of the composites

% HA	Copolymer	T _m (° C)	T _c (° C)	X _c (%)
0	0	164.3	121.3	62
30	0	163.1	120.1	45
30	10 (Polybond® 1001)	165.9	128.9	53
30	10 (Polybond® 1002)	165.9	129.4	50
0	10 (Polybond® 1001)	164.9	125.0	52*
0	10 (Polybond® 1002)	165.3	125.0	56*

* Calculated using the melt enthalpy of pure PP.

The thermal stability of the composites can be seen in table 4. The initial decomposition temperature of PP increases with the addition of HA. On the other hand, the blends of PP with the copolymers displayed lower activation energy values. This fact is attributed to the presence of carboxylic groups from the acrylic acid in the copolymers, which decreases the thermal stability of the polymeric matrix. Nonetheless, when the compatibilizers are incorporated into the composites, both the initial decomposition temperature and activation energy increase. Thus, the thermal stability of the composites with the compatibilizing agents is higher. This could also be a consequence of an improved interaction between the polymeric phase and the filler in the presence of the copolymers.

CONCLUSIONS

Polypropylene/hydroxyapatite composites revealed an increase of the Young's modulus and a decrease in the elongation at break with the addition of the filler. The addition of the copolymers did not affect the mechanical properties.

The crystallinity degree of PP decreased when the HA was incorporated, due to a hindered crystallization process in the presence of HA particles. HA produced a nucleating effect in composites containing the compatibilizing agents which could be a consequence of a slight increase in the degree of compatibility and/or dispersion of the filler. The presence of the compatibilizing agents in the composites increases their thermal stability.

The obtained results did not ascertain a real interaction between the polymeric phase and the filler when the compatibilizers are present in the composite.

Table 4. Thermal decomposition parameters of the composites.

% HA	Copolymer	Tid (° C)	Ea (kJ/mol)
0	0	340	305
30	0	360	306
30	10 (Polybond® 1001)	400	345
30	10 (Polybond® 1002)	380	346
0	10 (Polybond® 1001)	300	208
0	10 (Polybond® 1002)	360	177

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the financial support from Decanato de Investigación y Desarrollo de la Universidad Simón Bolívar and from Instituto Venezolano de Investigaciones Científicas.

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